

CLINICAL AND LABORATORY INDICATORS FOR ATYPICAL PNEUMONIA IN CHILDREN, TAKING INTO ACCOUNT AGE

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Pneumonia is an acute infectious disease of the pulmonary parenchyma, diagnosed by the syndrome of respiratory disorders or physical data in the presence of focal or infiltrative changes on the X-ray. The presence of these radiological signs is a "gold standard", according to WHO, with a high degree of probability, indicates the bacterial etiology of the process and makes it possible to exclude from the range of diseases defined as pneumonia most lesions of the lower respiratory tract: bronchitis, including obstructive, caused by respiratory viruses and not requiring antibacterial treatment [1,2].

The aim of the study was to evaluate clinical and laboratory signs of atypical pneumonia in children, taking into account age.

Materials and methods: In order to identify the main clinical and laboratory indicators of SARS, taking into account age and clinical picture, 60 sick young children with AP without coinfection and 60 sick young children with AP in coinfection were selected. We evaluated 21 clinical and 10 laboratory and instrumental signs characteristic of atypical pneumonia in children.

Results and discussion.

In order to identify the main clinical and laboratory indicators of SARS, taking into account age and clinical picture, 60 young children with AP without coinfection and 60 young children with AP in coinfection were selected. We evaluated 21 clinical and 10 laboratory and instrumental signs characteristic of atypical pneumonia in children.

As a result of the calculation, reliable information was obtained that SARS in young children is characterized by clinical signs with a high degree of association with coinfection:

- Fever of 38° and above -X2 -19.44;
- rashes on the body - X2 -34,286;
- night sweating- X2 -50,134.

Of the paraclinical indicators with a high strong association with coinfection in AP in young children, there were:

- pulmonary nodule on the X-ray- X2 -50,719;
- increased procalcitonin in the blood - X2 -43.248.

Clinical signs have been identified with a relatively strong association with coinfection in AP in young children:

- runny nose/nasal congestion - X2 -23,177;
- rhinorrhea- X2 -14,400;
- noisy BREATHING- X2 -16,416;
- perioral cyanosis- X2 -18.15;
- wet wheezing in the lungs- X2 -12.626;
- percussion sound of the lungs unchanged- X2 -10,812;
- muffling of heart tones - X2 -19.749;
- ear pain/otomycosis- X2 -11.109.

Of all the studied laboratory parameters, the relatively strong association was:

- lymphocytosis- X2 -19.749;
- the symptom of a "halo or sickle" on the MSCT of the lungs - X2 -14.070;
- increased blood IgE- X2 -14,830;
- increased IL-17A in the blood - X2 -25,350.

Then, at the second stage of the work, 60 sick children aged 4-7 years with AP without coinfection and 60 sick children aged 4-7 years with AP in coinfection were selected for a comparative assessment of the studied indicators, taking into account the age of children. We evaluated 21 clinical and 10 laboratory and instrumental signs characteristic of atypical pneumonia in children. The Chi of the square, the two-sided Fisher criterion, the normalized value of the Pearson coefficient and the bond strength for the two-by-two matrix were calculated simultaneously in an online calculator.

A comparative assessment of the strength of the association with coinfection of the studied clinical and laboratory parameters allowed us to identify the features of clinical symptoms in preschool children (4-7 years old). It has been established that atypical pneumonia in preschool children is characterized by clinical signs with a strong connection:

- Fever 38° and above -X2 -43.248;
- noisy BREATHING - X2 -13,468;
- rashes on the body - X2 -20,886;
- nosebleeds- X2 -12,102;
- perioral cyanosis- X2 -18,039;
- night sweats – X2 -11.760;
- chest pain -X2 -13,811.

Of all the studied laboratory parameters, a very strong association in AP in preschool children is an increase in the level of procalcitonin in the blood, while X2 is -71,810. Procalcitonin is followed by IL-17A (- X2-45,384) with a strong association and the pulmonary node on the lung X-ray in preschool patients -X2-37,136.

Conclusion

The features of clinical and laboratory parameters in AP in preschool children have been established, which consist in the absence of symptoms such as rhinorrhea, refusal to eat, wet wheezing in the lungs, normal percussion sound, weight loss and ear pain/otomycosis. With early detection and timely hospitalization of sick children with acute pneumonia in pediatric areas by pediatricians, it reduces the fatal outcome and the appointment of adequate therapy.

References:

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